

Bioaccumulation of Lead in Edible Vegetables Growing on Waste Dump Sites in Owerri, Nigeria: Implications for Public Health

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ABSTRACT:

Municipal waste dumps are likely to contain heavy metals including lead, whose contamination poses serious public health problems. This study examined the bioaccumulation of lead in vegetables growing in waste dump sites in Owerri and its environment. Eight (8) dump sites were visited, namely 1 dump at Avu, 3 dumps at Nekede, 2 dumps at Obinze. Other dumps visited were at Owerri municipal and portharcourt road. Of the eight dump site sample, edible vegetables were growing only in three: Avu and two dump sites at Nekede. The three edible vegetables collected were fluted pumpkin, water leaf and African spinach. The level of bio-accumulated lead in these edible vegetables were analyzed using atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS). The result from AAS showed that there was bioaccumulation of lead in African spinach and water leaf. There was no trace of lead in fluted pumpkin. African spinach has significantly the higher lead bioaccumulation of (0.15mg/kg) than water leaf (0.05mg/kg). Residents living around waste dump sites should be enlightened on the health effects of consuming vegetables growing in waste dump sites.

Keywords: Bioaccumulation, Lead, Dumpsites, Edible Vegetables

INTRODUCTION:

Heavy metals are generally referred to as those metals which possess a specific density of more than 5 g/cm³ and adversely affect the environment and living organisms. They, without doubt, are important constituents for plants and humans, when present only in small amount. Some micronutrient elements may also be toxic to both animals and plants at high concentrations. For instance, copper (Cu), chromium (Cr), fluorine (F), molybdenum (Mo), nickel (Ni), selenium (Se) or zinc (Zn). Other trace elements such as arsenic (As), cadmium (Cd), mercury (Hg) and lead (Pb) are toxic even at small concentrations. Heavy metals, being persistent and non-biodegradable, can neither be removed by normal cropping nor easily leached by rain water (Khan et al 2025). They might be transported from soil to ground waters or may be taken up by plants, including agricultural crops. For this reason, the knowledge of metal plant interactions is also important for the safety of the environment. There has been increasing interest in determining heavy metal levels in public food supplied. However, their concentration in bio-available form is not necessarily proportional to the total concentration of the metal

(Mohammadi et al 2020; Rai et al 2019). The quality of ecosystem becomes altered, when heavy metals find their ways somehow, into it through human and natural activities. These activities are one of the most pressing concerns of urbanization in developing countries like Nigeria, which result in the problem of solid, liquid and toxic waste management. Such waste may be toxic or radioactive, Such waste management problems include heaps of uncontrolled garbage, roadsides littered with refuse, streams blocked with rubbish, prevalence of automobile workshops and service stations, inappropriately disposed toxic waste and disposal sites that constitute a health hazard to residential areas (Khan et al 2015; Muchuweti et al 2006; Jarup, 2003).

Open dumps are a source of various environmental and health hazards. The decomposition of organic materials produces methane, which may cause explosions and produce leachates, which pollute surface and ground water. It ruins the aesthetic quality of the land. Automobile wastes include solvents, paints, hydraulic fluids, lubricants and stripped oil sludge; all results of activities such as battery charging, welding and soldering, automobile body works engine servicing and combustion processes (Rai et al 2019; Singh et al 2016;

Ratten et al 2005). It was observed that plants suffer oxidative stress that damages the cells and interfere with the ionic homeostasis when exposed to heavy metals (Singh et al 2016; Sharma et al 2007).

It is a common knowledge that there is high potential that heavy metals including lead are present waste dump sites because of disposal of industrial wastes, sewages, batteries etc. Also, it is a common site seeing people scavenging the dump sites as well as harvesting edible vegetables growing on dump sites. People also use the manure from this waste dump site to grow their crops and vegetables. The contamination of the environment and exposure of our food and water by heavy metal such as lead has serious public health implications.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study Area:

The study was conducted in Owerri. Owerri comprise of 3 Local Governments Areas namely; Owerri Municipal, Owerri West and Owerri North all located in Imo State

Sample Size:

The sample population consists of edible vegetables growing in waste dumps in Owerri and its environments

Data collection:

Waste dumps in Owerri, Municipal, Avu, Nekede. Obinze and Port Harcourt road were visited and samples of edible vegetables growing on them were counted. Samples of those edible vegetables were collected and identified. This exercised was carried out during the months of March to August 2023. The samples collected from the waste dump sites were taken to the

laboratory for analysis using Atomic absorption spectrometry (AAS).

Sample Preparation Procedures Steps:

The vegetables were carefully uprooted and washed thoroughly to remove adhering soil particles with clean tap water and separated into roots and shoots using a sharp knife. Fresh subsamples of each vegetable were taken and weighed immediately after sampling to determine the fresh weight.

Vegetable leaves and stems were totally smashed by pounding (each of the vegetables separately) and turned into a beaker. A conical flask was placed on an electronica weighing balance, each sample was taken with a spatula from the beaker into the conical flask until the sample weighs 10g respectively. 30ml of aqua regia (a minimum of two or three acids) was used to dilute each of the sample. Nitric and hydrochloric acid 84ml and 56ml respectively was used for the digestion of the samples in the ratio of 3:2 the color of aqua regia is burnt orange. Digestion is done further by boiling the sample, for each sample to have a complete digestion (in a pot of water) each sample is said to have digested completely, when the brownish foam has dried off or disappeared. After digestion, each sample is filtered using a filter paper in a funnel, and the solvent is being made up to 50ml by pouring distilled deionized water. The concentration of Pb in the solutions were read using the Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) (Agbenin, 1995).

Data analysis:

The data was presented in tables bearing decimal readings and standard calibration curve.

Plate 1-3 Vegetables seen at the dump sites

Plate 1: Fluted pumpkin (*Telfairia occidentalis*) Ugu leaf

Plate 2: Water leaf (*Talinum triangulare*)

Plate 3: African spinach (*Amaranthus cruentus*)

RESULTS:

Table 1 presents Edible vegetables growing on waste dumps in Owerri Municipal and its environment. From the table, eight (8) waste dump sites were visited in Owerri Municipal and its environment between May and June 2023. These sites were at Avu (1 site), 3 sites at Nekede and 2 sites at Obinze and one site each at PortHarcourt road and Owerri Municipal. Of all the eight waste dump sites, only three of them (37.5%) were observed to have growth of edible vegetables.

Table 2 presents Bio-accumulation of Lead in each of the edible vegetables growing in this waste dump sites. Atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS) was used to analyze the samples.

Result shows that fluted pumpkin have no trace of lead in it as a result of its fibrous tissue not being able to absorb much water from the soil unlike African spinach and water leaf. Seconded by African spinach which from the first and second run has 0.15 and 0.05 respectively having an average of 0.10mg/kg. thirdly, waterleaf was seen to have 0.05 and 0.05 in the first and second run respectively, having an average of 0.05mg/kg.

Table 1: Edible vegetables growing on waste dumps

S/N	Waste dump site	Edible vegetables and number observed		
		Fluted pumpkin	Water leaf	African spinach
1.	Avu site	0	12	2
2.	Nekede site 1	0	0	0
3.	Nekede site 2	3	1	1
4.	Nekede site 3	1	2	3
5.	Owerri Municipal site	0	0	0
6.	Obinze site 1	0	0	0
7.	Obinze site 2	3	5	1
8.	Port Harcourt Road site	0	0	0
	Total	7	20	7

Table 2: Analysis of Bio-accumulation of Lead in Edible Vegetables

S/N	Vegetable	AAS Reading (mg/kg)			Method
		Run 1	Run 2	Average	
1	Fluted pumpkin	ND	ND	–	AAS
2	African spinach	0.15	0.05	0.10	AAS
3	Waterleaf	0.05	0.05	0.05	AAS

DISCUSSION:

Generally, waste dump sites can either be permanent or temporal. In several cases, the temporal waste dump sites are usually evacuated to the permanent sites.

Because of these regular transfers of dump from the temporal sites, growth of edible vegetables are not usually progressive. The permanent waste dump sites tend to produce more vegetables because they are

relatively undisturbed. This enables the manure to form thereby improving the successful growth of edible vegetables. More so, the humidity, rainfall and sunlight contribute to the successful growth of plants and vegetables in the permanent waste dump sites. Apparently, it was observed that fluted Pumpkin, Water Leaf, African Spinach were growing in three permanent waste dump sites. The reason aforementioned contributed to their growth. These waste dump sites were Avu waste dump site, Obinze waste dump site and Nekede waste dump site.

Of the three edible vegetables collected, and analyzed, result from atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS) shows that only two has the result of bio-accumulation of lead in them and they are water leaf and African spinach.

The average value of lead found in these edible vegetables are 0.10mg/kg of African spinach, 0.05mg/kg of water leaf and none found in fluted pumpkin.

This result shows that African spinach has the highest number of leads in it seconded by water leaf while fluted pumpkin has none. The present result is not uncommon because heavy metals such as cadmium, Nickel have been identified to bio-accumulate in living organisms (Neha et al 2022; Khan et al 2015).

Lead is a toxic element that can be harmful to plants, although plants usually show ability to accumulate large amounts of lead without visible changes in their appearance or yield. Lead accumulates in the skeleton and its mobilization from bones during pregnancy and lactation causes exposure to fetuses and breastfed infants (Muchuweti et al 2006). In many plants, lead accumulation can exceed several hundred times the threshold of maximum level permissible for human. It has been suggested that lead on a cellular and molecular level may permit or enhance carcinogenic events involved in DNA damage, DNA repair, and regulation of tumour suppressor and promoter genes (Neha et al 2022).

Plants grown in lead-contaminated soils accumulate low levels of lead in the edible portions of the plant from adherence of dusts and translocation into the tissues (Li, 2010).

It's a common knowledge that waste dumps are created in Owerri municipal and its environment and those wastes dumps are likely to contain heavy metals such as lead. Dump sites are rich in humus thereby creating an enabling environment for vegetables to grow. It's of a great worry that people are seen to be collecting humus from the dump sites to use as manure in their farmland thereby, contaminating the vegetables produced by lead and other heavy metals which pose public health risk during consumption. During the study, it was evident that some people were harvesting the vegetables that were grown in those waste dump site and these waste dump sites are, Avu waste dump sites, Nekede waste dump site 1, and Nekede waste dump. sites 2. Some scavengers were seen to be harvesting those fluted pumpkin, African spinach and waterleaf. without

knowing that they have some levels bio-accumulated lead in them. The scavenging people may contaminate their hands with lead while scavenging the waste dump and the possible consumption of vegetables collected from those dumps may constitute health risk to them.

Lead accumulation in the environment is constantly increasing due to increase anthropogenic activities. The presence of these vegetables growing in dump sites was as a result of the decomposed manure and organic matter that was transferred from the temporal dumpsite to the permanent dumpsite. The permanency of dump site will determine whether or not vegetables will be growing in them. Due to the increase in population and human activities, there is still a need for more focused research to evaluate the effectiveness of bioremediation methods. Moreover, advancements are required for the effectiveness of new environmentally friendly remediation strategies which can help mitigate lead toxicity.

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